

Caer Melyn (Camelot) - Cosmic Hillfort of the King

The Yellow Hill (fort) as a Cosmic Hill or mountain motif and symbol of a King's authority

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May, 2019

ABSTRACT

The existence of a real Camelot should not be doubted. But the Yellow Fort is not in England, since it was always in Wales where the original British kings lived, in Glamorgan and Gwent. There were 38 generations from Brutus of Troy to King Arthur II (Arthwys), who is the Arthur of the round table (Cybwr). In the locating of Caer Melyn, the work has already been performed, however, has the cosmic significance been grasped? In this paper, the author looks at the location and description of the real Camelot from the perspective of the Saturn (and Jupiter) Myth, using some of its archetypes and motifs, in order to ultimately evaluate its relationship to the Divine Right to Rule, and the rose-colored memory of a shining castle on a hill.

Keywords: Camelot - Arthur - Round Table - Saturn - Yellow - Earth - Rome

Synopsis

The kingdom of Glamorgan¹ and Gwent was the seat of original British power for almost a thousand years from the time of Brutus, a descendant of Aeneas of Troy², until the fall of Wales 1282-1283 AD³ under King Edward I of England.⁴ The Khumry were the British lords when Caesar began his attempts to conquest, and after his double defeat at invasion, they found a way for tenuous agreement in 'colonization' via barter of culture and bloodlines. This ended with King Arthmael (Arthur I) who invaded Europe on behalf of the emperor Magnus Maximus, his grandfather in the 3rd century AD. From there forward well through King Arthwys (Arthur II) and Arthur III, the seat of power was in Caerleon, Cerniw, and most famously Camelot. As Alan Wilson and A.T "Baram" Blackett have revealed in their groundbreaking, unique research based on primary Welsh resources, Camelot was in the original Khumry/Cumry, termed not Cornwall (as Cerniw is not in England), but Caer Melyn. Caer means a hill fort made of stone, and Melyn means yellow.⁵ They remark that in the search for the real Caer Melyn there are several in Welsh history, including 2 in the south⁶ and 1 in the north of Wales. However, within short distance to Caerleon/Fort Hill there is only one hill, now located at the place near to Thornhill known as Yellow Farm (51.55588, -3.17531), which has the requisite shape (see Figure 1) and, most importantly ancient, unexcavated (at the time) fort-shaped earthworks⁷.

But while Wilson and Blackett attribute the name of the hill to several sulphur springs on the hill, could there be an EPEMC explanation for the hill's choice, and meaning, beyond the convenience of the sulphur springs (which would themselves be very fortuitous)⁸? In short, the Saturn and Jupiter Myths say: yes.

Figure 1 - Topographic Layout of Caer Melyn

¹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Glamorgan>

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Brutus_of_Troy

³ http://www.bbc.co.uk/wales/history/sites/themes/guide/ch8_end_of_welsh_independence.shtml

⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Conquest_of_Wales_by_Edward_I_of_England

⁵ This discussion will be found in "Artorius Rex Discovered," pp. 30-61

⁶ The other being Castlefield, also in south Wales, if it is not Caerleon itself.

⁷ It's important to note that Khumry/British **Caer** were not castles as we imagine them. They were stone-earthwork combinations, with wooden rafters. They were designed around a different ideal of defense: the ring kingdom. See the King Arthur Conspiracy Map for an example. <http://bit.ly/2XKG86l>

⁸ And only 4.2 miles from Taff's Well, the only hot springs in South Wales
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Taff%27s_Well_Thermal_Spring

Where is Camelot?

Typically, mainstream Anglo-Saxon archaeology, which has only recently admitted that British people are descended of the ancient Middle East⁹ though all the British myths recorded by the Khumry say this¹¹, denies the reality of Arthur and the myths carte blanche. This is, of course as quackish and looney as the manifold bizarre Arthurian theories which rely on interpreting known Renaissance fiction as fact. For example, interpreting Cerniw as Cornwall, and Tintagel - a monastery - as Camelot. This is asinine since the Italian, Spanish, and French myths were clearly derived from Brittany, a Welsh colony from the conquests of Arthur I, and not from the later Normans, and certainly not from Anglo-Saxons. The difference is obvious: in Wales stones covered in Coelbren¹² - a script which can be used to translate Etruscan and Hebrew¹³ - litter the countryside even still¹⁴. This is simply not the case for Saxony England (Loegria as it was once called), where the most famous stones are sarsen stones, devoid of ancient writing. In Wales, also are the Llandaff Charters¹⁵ which attest to the reality of a Glamorgan kingdom, and hints of an empire that was able to control the entire island. Other works elsewhere attest conquests that covered Ireland and France, and even down into Italy. The mainstream does not share the opinion of Wilson & Blackett that the Roman emperors are Welsh, but a clear list of parallel names exists which shows very clearly that they did (see Table 2).

The bottom line, however, is that in modern times Arthurian tales are viewed as myths and fairy tales, worthy of cartoons and a few movies, but as time goes on people become more and more disconnected from stark realities of Dark Age battle, culture, socio-religio-geopolitics, and of course logistics and culture barriers. Fantasy and romanticism have their place in literary fiction, but not in research. When considering the actual facts, one must shed oneself of preconceived notions about the Arthurian myths (see Table 1).

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<https://www.dailymail.co.uk/sciencetech/article-1244654/Study-finds-Britons-descended-farmers-left-Iraq-Syria-10-000-years-ago.html>

¹⁰ <https://www.theguardian.com/science/2018/feb/10/cheddar-man-changed-way-we-think-about-ancestors>

¹¹ In fact Wilson & Blackett maintain that the Khumry migrated in this way: Israel > Troy > Crimea > Italy/Etrusca > Wales

¹² The true authenticity of Coelbren has been treated somewhat in author's previous work, [28]

¹³ "King Arthur Conspiracy," Wilson & Blackett (G. Berkley), pp.137-290

¹⁴ "Wales: History in Bondage," JoLe Productions,

https://www.joleproductions.com/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=6&Itemid=3

¹⁵ See "The Holy Kingdom," A. Gilbert and "Arthur and the Charter of the Kings," Wilson & Blackett

Table 1 - Arthurian Fact vs. Myth

Myth	Fact
Arthur isn't real	There were 4 Arthurs ¹⁶ : Arthfael I; Arthwys ¹⁷ ; Arthfael ¹⁸ II; Arthfael III
Guinevere betrayed Arthur with Sir Lancelot who is really King Maelgwyn of North Wales	Gwenhwyfar, 2nd wife of Arthur ¹⁹ , betrayed him with Medrawd (Modred), and was put to death
Arthur I defeated the Romans and the Saxons	Arthur I, the Romans, Arthur II routed the Saxons; a difference of more than 150 years
Cerniw is in Cornwall	Cerniw is in Cardiff and terminates at Arthur's Head
Merlin is a wizard who advises and teaches Arthur	Myrddin Wylt (Martin the Wild) from North Brython ²⁰ who is cited as Merlin has nothing to do with Arthur. Merlin Elwyg is a Bard from North Wales ²¹ and may have instructed Arthur from age 7
A physical sword in an anvil or stone	Stone moulds were an iron age improvement; but as for carvings on a sword referring to a "king, born of England" are pure fantasy.
Quest for the holy grail	The grail quest was a metaphor, and nothing to do with a cup; but the Ark of the Covenant may have reached Britain, as per Wilson & Blackett, via St. Joseph of Arimathea ²²
The forts and walls of the iron age, are built by Romans, Normans, or Saxons	Saxons did not build castles but inherited them; the Normans built entirely different castles and in the later centuries; and the Romans settlements had been much earlier, and were all in decline, and besides they were borrowed techniques by the British so as to live in Roman style

¹⁶ The author has created a dynamic family tree for public use:
<https://www.geni.com/family-tree/index/6000000092212236940>

¹⁷ "... the Legendary Round Table Kind. Buried in the Cave of Pavilions in the Forest of Mystery. The Uthyr Pendragon III, well attested in all records The stones of his brothers Pawl and Idnerth are at Merthyr Mawr and Llandewi Brefi." p. 26

¹⁸ "...Arthur III, said to have married Cenhedlon of Powys. Actually the brother of King Howell and King Meurig who is misnamed as his son. Probably [this is] the King Arthur who defeated the army of Rhodri Mylwonog at Pencoed in 721 A.D. This King said to be buried at St. Margaret's Church in Cardiff." Ibid. p.27

¹⁹ Daughter of Ogyrvran Gawr, married 549 A.D., vs. the first Gwenhwyfar, daughter of Garawyd Ceint, and vs. the third wife, daughter of Gwythyr Mawr, married 562 A.D. The first died naturally, but the second was torn to pieces by his hounds. Ibid. pp.130-131

²⁰ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Merlin>

²¹ A fortress at Deganwy at the very north of Wales.

²² "Maelgwyn of Llandaff and Joseph of Arimathea," 'A. Kelly' (Wilson & Blackett), 2013

Table 2 - List of British Lords and Parallel Roman Emperors²³

British King	Roman Emperor
Alan Alerw ap Ysbwyth	Antonnius Pius c. 138-161
King Meirchion Vawdilwyr	Marcus Anninus Aurelius Verus c. 161
King Lleirwg	Lucius Aurelius Verus c. 161-169
Crallo ap Lleirwg	Commodus Britannicus c. 179-192
The Legate of Britain	Publius Helvius Pertinax c. 192
King Corrwg/Gorwg	Didius Clodius Septimus Albinus c. 192-197
Severini	Lucius Septimus Severis ²⁴ c. 192-211
King Gorddyfwn	Marcus Aurelius Antonnius Caracallus c. 211-218
King Gwrthl	Publius Septimus Geta c. 209-211
King Meirchion ap Rhun	Marcus Opellinus Severus Macrinus c. 217-218
King Ensyth	Varius Avitus Elagabalus ²⁵ c. 218-222
King Arthfael	Marcus Aurelius Alexander Severus c. 222-235
King Gwrgan Ffrych	Gaius Julius Varus Maximianus c. 235-238
King Meurig ap Meirchion	Maximinianus Clodius Pupienus Maximus c. 238
King Crair - Carawn ap Meurig	Carausius Emperor of Britain ²⁶ c. 286-293
King Casnar Wledig ap Carawn	Chrysanthus Asciepiodotus, Legate of Britain
King Meuric ap Casnar	Maxentius ²⁷
King Mascen Wledig ap Llewellyn	Magnus Maximus ²⁸

The next step, therefore, is to determine, within linguistic possibility and geographical reasoning using rationalism, what would make sense? We live now in an age of convenience and more importantly, *speed*.

In the modern day, it is possible to leave London and drive to Scotland within a single day, or to visit the Ettenmoors, if so desired. One can even drive under the ocean and arrive in France within a couple hours, despite traffic. That is, of course, insanelly different than the experience of the Normans, Saxons, Celts, Picts,

²³ "Artorius Rex Discovered," pp. 18-19

²⁴ "Tombstone in North Wales"

²⁵ Marcus Aurelius Antoninus; Gessius Bassianus Alexianus adopted as his heir

²⁶ "Tombstone in Wales" (location not given)

²⁷ "Usurped the kingdom of Britain and Gaul in 350-353"

²⁸ "Usurped the Empire of the West in 383-388"

Scots, Vikings, Vandals/Mercians, and Khumry. The number of difficulties that would be experienced by a traveler, immigrant, invader, sailor, or pilgrim in the Dark Ages is extremely numerous, whereas now we have come to expect, barring any major accident at high speed, to arrive very quickly and safely within a reasonable period of time. This has led to all sorts of comical misunderstandings of medieval logistics, such as seen in the “Lord of the Rings,” movie translation, or the “Game of Thrones” adaptation, where individuals seem to know what is happening far elsewhere. In the case of “Lord of the Rings,” elves are prescribed hilarious psychic and teleportation powers in order to drive the plot, because the tension of the writer-adapter’s narrative falls apart under the original, more realistic timeline written by J.R.R. Tolkien, a renowned professor of linguistics of northern cultures. In short, to explain the movement of peoples, and news of their movements which would instigate responses in other cultures in the effect of slow moving waves rather than instant telephony, requires a good deal more realistic planning. A writer would, in effect, without the benefit of history as Wilson & Blackett have in the Welsh stones, need to utilize extensive planning and calculation. The effect of the absence of these plans can actually bamboozle the modern person because, after all, they are quite used to cars and telephony.

Consider, as an exercise, the rendering of horses in popular media: they are driven forth as fast beasts you simply wheel about wherever you want to go. If one should die in war, you just get another (a thought-product of a disposable culture such as ours). If you fall from one you just get right back on, and whip the darn thing, as you would hammer an engine when it makes you angry. In a charge against pikes they just run right into, through, or jump over them.

This is sheer nonsense. Horses are powerful living creatures. Some cultures, such as the Scots-Irish prefer to capture wild ones, and break them. The effect, of course, is increased *horsepower*, and by proxy danger. If a horse is killed in battle it is a game changer for that warrior, because they must wit to acquire and break in a new horse, unless a herd has been brought with them, and painstakingly offloaded from ship, or protected from theft in overland movement. In the movement of messengers, they either must have a relay system of fresh horses every so often, perhaps 20 miles or so, or the message must come slowly.

Wilson & Blackett, therefore, had to work out their timeline based not only upon the written record, but reasonability. They have done so. But more importantly they have provided the means to explain the effective defensive abilities of the Bruts. These defensive ideas undoubtedly span back to Troy, or even to Jerusalem. First and foremost, the castles are placed on hilltops. This would not be effective, as a student of the Art of War would attest, on their own, for a castle or fort (*caer*) would simply be surrounded, and starved or deprived of water access, until it fell within a few weeks. However the second aspect, is that the forts, manned by the very peasantry and husbands that people the vales, would be defended by sure knowledge of approach even before the approaching army was seen from the high position of the hillfort. Finally, the Welsh-British lords had a final decided advantage: the ring system. See Figure 2.

The net effect of this is to, more or less, pinpoint the likely position of a hillfort. In the case of Caerleon, it is not hard to find, for the town is still named as such. The only difficulty is in the propensity of the mainstream Anglo-Saxon archaeology to regard the nearby Roman fort ruins, built during temporary occupation during a time of treachery of Boudica²⁹ (and Cogibdinus and others³⁰) as the real Caerleon. However, this is impossible as it is not located atop a hill but on the river Usk, a decided disadvantage. It must have been a hastily chosen port-town.

²⁹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Boudica>

³⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Treachery_of_the_Long_Knives

Figure 2 - Caerleon Fort System; credit: Wilson & Blackett³¹

No, instead Wilson & Blackett have identified the true site, which has unfortunately been devastated by the development of a suburb of Cardiff, at Lodge Hill, very near to the Hospital.

It is situated as seen in Figure 2, almost centrally to the ring of forts which would have communicated via firelight or reflecting glass (using the sun during the day). So what about Camelot? What would it be to approach the famous seat of power? Firstly, one can be assured it would not be on the coast, nor even in the center of the ring next to the coast, but it would be near enough to unleash protection in case of invasion. It was likely chosen in long ago times for this ability after the Romans made sudden onslaught under Caesar, who was unsuccessful after two attempts to take the island by force.

There are only two such locations of choice, that of Castlefield, and that of our chosen location. The name Castlefield does not seem to inspire much into the explanation of the word "Cam'lot" itself likely a French barbarism of the original. While it is situated proximal to Llantwit Major, it is, after all a field and not a hillfort. It was known as the Yellow Fort³². Suffice it to say, there is nothing to indicate this is a well chosen site for the High King's residence. Instead it seems to be a 'home away from home' (and hence mentioned enough to be

³¹ Ibid. p. 31

³² 51.43584, -3.49878

called Camelot), on the south-western outposts. Not nigh to the coast, but nigh enough to watch for Irish invaders and occupy if invaders manage to penetrate long enough.

Comparatively, Gaer Fawr³³ would be a much more likely alternative, but unlike our location, it is not currently guarding the bay. Its ring of hillforts sit just north of the mouth of the bay. As for the kingdom of Brecon, there's nothing to indicate that King Arthur could afford to abide so far from the coast. Again, a smart system would be to have rings of forts that abutt and provide dual layers of protection from invaders. Communications with the interior of Wales would be far too slow to place Camelot in the far north or even in Brecon. Attempts to put the ancient kingdom in North Wales are critically weak, for all invasions come either from the south, or to Scotland (Pictland) in the very north of Britain, where Arthur II (Arthwys) made war, destroying the allies of Irish, Picts, Scots, and Saxons all of which invaded there. It isn't that North Wales had no part, it was, of course, the source of trouble for the Civil War, brought about by Medrawd's taking of Camelot and the 2nd wife of Arthur (See Table 1) while he was away in Brittany. The "youth" (of about age 40) felt it was his time to rise in power, and mistakenly took the maiden. However, he lost a decisive battle on the beach (proving his ineptitude as a king), and fled north. He was pursued to the death by a relentless Arthur, who may have been wounded by poisoned spear in this pursuit, but who lived and came south again to marry a 3rd wife, and bear children a third time, before dying only a few years after his father, King Maurice (Meurig ap Tewdrig).

One other thing should be mentioned: the kings of Wales controlled their rings, but they elected via counsel of Kings or the High King Lord. Although the lineage of kings went from Theoderic to Maurice to Arthur II, (it was not always so,) and thus Modred's rebellion occurred when he was no longer Edling (as Morgan had usurped this position). He was fighting for his right to be the premier King and win the vote of High King. However, he was not able to win, for the line of Tewdrig was cunning both politically and militarily. Arthur was, in the main, an undefeated "bear" as his name suggests.

Zeroing In on the location

Ignoring the Caer part (as there are 500 forts around Wales), Wilson & Blackett say,

"...we have to concentrate on the second part, Melyn or Melin or something close to that.... The colour naming principle is immediately attractive and worth examining, for we have [also] "White" forts, "Red" forts, "Black" forts, and so on. The word ending "Melot" in Norman French sees to have affinities with the Welsh word Melyn - Yellow, and other languages have similar words for this colour. We find the Greek word is 'Melinos' meaning 'apple coloured' or yellow, and the Latin 'Melleus' meaning 'honeyed'.... We were conscious that the ancient Roman town Melodnum in Gaul means 'din-mael' or the fort of steel, now it is Melun, but Melyn as Yellow was the word which seemed to offer the best possibility in the Welsh context....

"East of Lisvane - which means the "Court of the Van", on the road to Cefn Mably, there lies the site of an unidentified ancient fort. Its position is magnificently chosen for it dominates the whole of the Cardiff plain where the city now stands. Its situation is on the end of a spur of land which extends from the East end of the very steep Cefn On ridge.... The visible mounds show that this was obviously a Caer of some importance, for considerable work has been done to build a large abutment on one side to carry the defensive mound walls... More importantly it lies close to two very old farms, one is called Bethllwyds Church Farm, and the other is Yellow Wells Farm. The Yellow Wells is so called because there were anciently sulphur pits on the land, and in Welsh it would be Ffynnon Melyn... the name of the fort would therefore be Caer Melyn, which is easily corrupted into Camelot in Norman French....

³³ 51.68037, -2.80752

“Geographically the fort is right where it should be, for there was clearly a place of the laws close at hand.... The area dominated by this caer is anciently known as part of the Commote of Cibbor, also spelled... Cibbwr... The name has never been satisfactorily explained in modern terms, but... We seem to have Cy and Bwr,... ‘Cy’ indicates a mutual action, something done together. The second word ‘Bwr’ is more difficult and seems to be a version of Bwrdd which means “table”, and if this is the case then we have “Cybwr” meaning simply - “Mutually together at the table.””³⁴ (In effect, the round table).

They go on to explain generally the concept of laws, councils, and more details which add to their case. But before they explain the Cybwr/Kibbor more fully and go on to describe the wheel of defense, they have this to add:

“The Military court was the Court at Caerleon, surrounded by the ring of outpost forts of Goldcliffe at Wilcrick, at Kemeys at Cae Camp, at Llanfrechfa at Castell-y-bwych at Twmbarlwm, at Rhiwderin at Maes Arthur, at Gaern and so back to Goldcliff. The administrative centre is similarly surrounded by a ring of fortresses also set in a great circle. The Court of Caer Melying.... Is surrounded by first Cardiff Castle, and then going anti-clockwise, Penylan Fort, then one at Cae Castell, at Penylan-Cerniw, at Maes Arthur, at Rhiwderin, at Twmbarlwm, at Mynydd Machen, at Cefn Carnau, at Caer, at Arthur’s Buttresses, at Caerwigau, at Caer Trehil, at Caerau Carnau, and so back to Cardiff. Both the Caerleon Court and the Caermelyn Court are at the centre of the great rings of outpost forts...”
³⁵ (See Figure 3)

This would explain rather more completely, than the vague modern idea of “justice and democracy,” which has little to do with practical monarchical systems and civilizations, why there should be a round table, or if not a table, a flat plain of rounded forts, each visited in turn by the court. All the knights would essentially be dukes, and highly respected for their playing the part of guarding the entire ring’s safety. It would be, as far as feudal systems go, the most ideal and equitable manner in which to govern and mutually guard from invasion, a fair kingdom of agriculturalists, herders, and fisher-folk. The fairness of the system, as far as the Dark Ages is concerned, would be long remembered in the Bardic tradition, even if the meaning of Cybwr was forgotten. The hillforts generally remain, but the meaning has been more or less lost.

Please remember, reader, that the authors Wilson & Blackett were able to utilize the evidence in welsh stones to find, predict, and continue to find objects related to the Arthurian myths, up to and after the discovery of the Arthurian headstone, shown in Figure 4

³⁴ Ibid. pp.42-43

³⁵ Ibid. p. 46

Figure 3 - Caer Melyn Ring System, just west of the system in Figure 2; credit: Wilson & Blackett³⁶

Figure 4 - Rex Artorius, Fili Mauricius (King Arthur, son of Maurice); credit: Blackett & Wilson/Amazon Books³⁷

It may be considered strange that the headstone would be in latin rather than Coelbren, but this is only natural as the stone would have been commissioned by the Church, which was at the time still Roman Catholic. Latin was and remains to this day, considered the language of high civilization and science. Plus, as shown in Table 2, there are considerable Latin - British connections and influences, as the two civilizations intermingled during the Germanic conquests. Those who bristle at this idea need to explain why Romans in Germany is considered wide knowledge but nearby Britain be unable to travel also to Germany, Austria, Prussia, and Italy.

³⁶ Ibid. p.

³⁷ Copyright now George Horwatt, available at www.ancientkentucke.com

The Cosmic Hill

Where is it, thus, that we see a *grander* design or archetype, which emphasizes the hill and the king? One does not have to look very long, because in the previously discussed Saturn Myth (ala Talbot) there is an established motif, known as the Cosmic Hill, or Mountain (such as Olympus, Meru, Taishan, or Ararat), which demonstrates the idea completely. For ease of reference, the chart compiled by the author³⁸ may assist, or refer to Figure 5.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
		Egypt			Mesopotamian				Hebrew	Greece	
		Older	Middle	Newer	Sumerian	Babylonian	Akkadian	Other		Athens	Other
78	Circular Serpent	Mut	Set	ami khet	Tiamat	Esharra			Tehom	Chronos	Ophion, Pelor
79	Center of Circle Sun	ab								Helios	
80	Cosmic Mountain	Khut	Maa	Abtu	Kur	Hursag		Mithras	Zion	Olympus	Parnassus
81	Mooring Post/Palace at pole	Menat.Mena-uret	Tet	Khet	Dimgal	Tarkullu			Zaphon	Kiun	
82	Pedestal/backbone	Aat	Thes/Sep	An-mut-f					Ei		
83	The One-legged God	Akheku	Ptah/Set	Sept							
84	Masculine-pole serpent/dragon		Set		Kur	Ningirsu				Boreas	Asculapius
85	Aether/Ether-pillar	Shu			Lil				Wind		
86	Supporting fountain	ashesh			"pure Euphrates"						
87	Weapon of the gods				Sar-ur-u-sar-gaz	Bab-ba-nu-il-la					
88	The Night-Sun	Khensu/uraeus									
89	Moon-Earth Goddess	Aditi								Minerva	Rhea,Cybele,Jana
90	Paradise-land/Primeval land								Tyre,Ararat		
91	Cosmic double-mountain	atenti/ateriti							Nonnus,Horeb,Ebol,Gerezim		
92	Mountain of the Moon					Jura/Ira/Rhe			Laban		
93	Tripele-summit									Olympus	
94	Two faced/Twin Gods	herui				Sin/Nergal					Dioskoroi

Figure 5 - Cosmic Mountain Names in Oldest Cultures; credit: author³⁹

So without quoting the entire text, let us quickly re-assert the hypothesis of Dave Talbott (comparative mythologist) and contemporary colleague, engineer Wallace Thornhill (no relation to Arthur myth).

1. The primordial midnight sun and first God of mankind was Saturn/Shamash/Atum-Ra/Ptah/Kronos/EI
2. The then brown dwarf star was our cosmic warmer, and the Earth existed within its womb. The Father was the Mother (hence the hermaphroditic motifs, and incestuous references which New Kingdom Egyptians tried to fulfill in the time of Akhenaten).
3. The sky was purplish in that age, and the star was greenish. Hence plants evolved to reflect green, and many species failed to see blue or red differently from green.
4. The Earth was within the aten, or womb, before the "sky fell" (Ouranos/Uranus, the father of Kronos)
5. The star flared and exchanged plasma streamers with collinearly-aligned⁴⁰ planets Venus, Mars, and even Earth (possibly inviting the pyramid/piezoelectric⁴¹ power plant⁴² age in Giza).
6. Eventually Jupiter/Zeus overthrew the father Kronos, and tossed him into Tartarus (the void). He was 'chained' as rings formed. Then Earth and Mars and Venus 'went for a ride' on account of the failed electro-gravitics⁴³ of Kronos. Venus appeared to be birthed of Saturn, and perhaps it was ripped from

³⁸ <http://bit.ly/2BoN0hk>

³⁹ As per D. Talbot, "The Saturn Myth"

⁴⁰ <https://www.velikovsky.info/wp-content/uploads/attachments/412.pdf>

⁴¹ <https://phys.org/news/2018-07-reveals-great-pyramid-giza-focus.html>

⁴² "Giza Power Plant," C. Dunn, 1998

⁴³ Literally energy-mass determined by charge density (quark related differentiation).

Saturn. Later it went through Jupiter, and Zeus battled the comet-tail called Typhon, and cosmic lightning was witnessed.

7. The Earth transitioned to Jovian quasi stable orbit, and temperatures dropped. Saturn's ring was visible, and the God's eye was fixed on mankind, and was also seen on Jupiter's red spot and poles⁴⁴. The calendar was now 300 days.
8. Both Jupiter and Saturn underwent further starvation of electrons in the intense solar wind, and eventually Earth, Mars, Mercury, and Venus all were brought by the sun into the warmer zones. Earth fell within the habitable zone, and the calendar slightly increased from the old 360 of Saturn to 365 days. This attests to the angular momentum. Around Jupiter the days would have been different in length and the transition may have introduced the world famed cosmic winds of destruction (Tai Feng). Evidence by Andy Hall of wind-blaster super heated mountains should be reviewed for further understanding.
9. The motifs of the Original God, and the flare event were passed along in the Jovian Age when El became Jehovah/IAO/Yao/Ywahoo/Shiva.
10. In the sky at that time there had been a step pyramid of plasma pinching flares, as per Dr. Peratt.
11. The stream from Venus and Mars in later cataclysms reinforced this mountain in the sky.
12. The Chinese recorded the transfer of power as a pulse along a spear or sword, in their words for Lightning and Thunder.⁴⁵
13. The Japanese revered the battles of Venus and Mars⁴⁶ (while the Babylonians saw it as mating), as there were cosmic "rope" (representing thunder, whose Chinese word meant earthquake) extending between the planets Venus and Mars. This battle inspired ages of war worldwide, and heart sacrifice amongst many aboriginals.
14. The difficult ages of cataclysm caused the worship of Zep Tepi in Egypt - the first time - or rule under Ra/Elohim/Osiris/Odin/Quetzalcoatl; or of that of Jove/Horus/Thor. The cosmic bird, ship, or floating city wherein a seeming pantheon of Jovian and far off Saturnian moons (the Aesir and Vanir, respectively) hovered and times were good. Agriculture was back, the Ice Ages were over. Conditions in the north were colder, and the balmy weather of northern continents and Orkney gave way to "frost giants", but generally the age was thought of as good or civilized. Travel worldwide became possible. Egypt and Sumer flourished and civilization had sprouted all over. But in the times from Exodus through the age of Buddha, life had been frightening, and war (such as the Iliad expressed, and the Zhou Dynasty), made mankind yearn for the Cosmic Paradise. Literally Ed-In, where the gods Enlil and Enki and Inanna had dwelt after Anu had departed.
15. The Cosmic Hill became associated with the cosmic ship or crescent of revolving light reflecting off the Midnight Sun, and also with the Paradise.

As Cardona records of Budge's lesser known translations,

*"I am the lord of the crown. I am in the Eye, my egg... **My seat is on my throne.** I sit in the pupil of the Eye." ~Papyrus of Ani (Budge)*

"he who entereth [or liveth] in the Circle." [aten], Gods of the Egyptians (Budge)

"the sender forth of light into his Circle." [the] "Lord of the Circles."

*"Thou hast come with thy splendours, and thou has made heaven and earth bright with thy rays of **pure emerald light**" ~Egyptian Book of the Dead*

⁴⁴ [30]

⁴⁵ [22]

⁴⁶ [27]

"O Ra... the heir of eternity, self-begotten and self-born kind, king of the earth, prince of the netherworld... thou dost rise in the horizon of heaven and sheddest upon the world beams of emerald light"

"Hail Green One!" Osiris & The Egyptian Resurrection (Budge)

"You shall go up upon the great West side of the sky, and go down upon the great East side of the earth." Coffin Texts (Spell)⁴⁷ (emphasis added)

And the Mayans opined,

*"It was in the year called one-reed. It is said that when he arrived at the sea, on the shore of the ocean, he stopped, cried, arranged his belongings, and got dressed in his finery, his **turquoise**⁴⁸ mask, etc. And when he had entirely prepared himself, he himself set himself on fire, **put himself into the flames**. And that is why it is called Tlatlayän, the place where Quetzalcöätl was burned. And they say that when he burned, his ashes rose up into the air, and there appeared, as they looked at it, all the rare birds, which flew upwards; and there were to be seen in the sky the spoonbills, the cotinga, the trogons, the herons the yellow-headed toznene perakeets, the ara, the white cocho perakeets, and all the other rare birds. And after his ashes there [were all gone], **then the heart of Quetzalcöätl rose up, as they saw, and according to their belief, and it went into the sky; it entered the sky**. The old people said that it changed into the star that appears at dawn⁴⁹ according to what they say, it appeared when Quetzalcöätl died, so they called it Tlahuizcalpantëuctli ("Lord of the Dawn"). According to what they said, when he died, it was not seen for four days. They said that then he went to dwell in the realm of the dead. And during the four days [there] he made darts⁵⁰, and at the end of eight days a great star appeared, which they called Quetzalcöätl, and **they said that he established himself in his realm**. And that was the whole life of the one called Quetzalcöätl who was born in the year one-reed and also died in the year one-reed. And they calculate that he lived a total of 53 years."⁵¹ (emphasis added)*

The evidence for all of this has been gathered elsewhere by the author⁵², J. Cook & J. West⁵³, G. Hancock⁵⁴, D. Talbot, and I. Velikovsky⁵⁵, among others. The evidence is actually overwhelming in physical evidence as well as mythic, linguistic, anthropological, and of course plasma produced in laboratory experiments. The mainstream itself moves towards plasma cosmology daily.⁵⁶

What we are interested in, therefore is the purpose of living atop of (or in the case of places like Cahokia, Avebury, Biggs Site, Canary Islands, Mauritania, Bosnia, Gobkli Tepe, China, etc.) hills. For example, the Cherokee revere Stone Mountain in the same light as aborigines of Australia revere Ayer's Rock, and the Lakota revere the Black Mountains in exactly the same manner as the Chinese do Wudang⁵⁷.

It is that these hills represent the Cosmic Mountain, but also the authority of the Great Man or God/Shang Di. It is said in China that the word for yang, which means sun, originally meant the bright side of the hill. The glyph for Ri - the sun - is a shape not representing the disc orb, but instead a hexagon originally,

⁴⁷ "God Star," D. Cardona

⁴⁸ In Chinese blue-green is also one word, "qing". Another word for mask in Chinese is black, also the color of water, and space. Hence the "separation of the water from the waters" in the Bible.

⁴⁹ That is Venus

⁵⁰ [27] and [28] have diagrams which the Chinese show the darts, which are plasma formations. As are the thunderbirds.

⁵¹ <http://pages.ucsd.edu/~dkjordan/nahuatl/ReadingQuetzalcoatl.html>

⁵² [2], [3], [4], [7], [8], [12], [16], [22], [24], [27], [28], [30]; summary tables found at: <http://bit.ly/2PwFKp5>

⁵³ "The Jupiter Myth"

⁵⁴ "Fingerprint of the Gods," and "Magicians of the Gods"

⁵⁵ "Worlds in Collision," and "Ages of Chaos," etc.

⁵⁶ <https://www.researchgate.net/project/Extended-Plasma-Electromagnetic-Cosmology-EPEMC>

⁵⁷ They say the mountains "lean in" upon one another. At Wudang they worship Zhenwu/Xuanwu - God of Thunder

as covered in previous works⁵⁸. This hexagon is not found on Jupiter, for its poles are the octagon and pentagram, as North and South pole, respectively. But the hexagon found in Kentucky rock art (as per Coy & Fuller⁵⁹) and in Chinese Shang oracle bones is only seen on the Saturnian North pole⁶⁰. It happens to be changing color now⁶¹ (all the atmospheres of the solar system are undergoing climate change, actually⁶²), probably due to the de-powering of Saturn, which still emits much more heat than it receives, but grows daily weaker⁶³.

What would the significance of worshiping certain “holy mountains” such as Mt. Meru, Sumeru, Mt. Tai, Olympus, and Mt. Ararat be? Could the arc-discharges of the aforementioned “darts” have raised mountains as world religions suggest? If not that, could it be that a cosmic hill or mountain was worthy of worship, and this, for example, might instigate the People of the Sun such as Cahokians or Moundville, Alabama, to raise huge mounds? The mound and pyramid building event was worldwide, and goes back well to before the Younger Dryas at Bosnia and Gunung Padang. So it cannot only be the flare. It would appear though that the step-streamers of the Z-pinching (what some termed a ladder or stairway to Heaven) was quite profound. It was enough to instigate the Babylonians to build the famed tower to the sky. They were not the only culture that became obsessed with skyscraping towers, for there were events of skyscraper formation in both Europe *and* southern China way up in the earthquake prone Himalayas.

Figure 6 - Lost Towers of Bologna, 11th Century A.D.

⁵⁸ [26], [28]

⁵⁹ Covered at length in [16], also see “Rock Art of Kentucky,” by Fuller et al...

⁶⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Saturn%27s_hexagon

⁶¹ <https://www.good.is/articles/saturn-north-pole-changing-color>

⁶² <https://news.agu.org/press-release/new-study-finds-evidence-of-changing-seasons-rain-on-titans-north-pole/>

⁶³ https://www.science20.com/news_articles/why_does_saturn_radiate_twice_energy_it_absorbs_sun

Figure 7 - Secret Towers of the Himalayas (few remain), suspected 5th-11th century A.D.

No one knows exactly why either culture decided to produce these towers, but Talbot maintains it was an advancement of the Cosmic Hill into the Cosmic Pole, at the top of which resided the Cosmic City/Paradise or Floating Island. It was also interpreted as two (or three) arms, a leg, a woman's groin, breasts, and a boat which road upon a female goddess (such as Nuut), upside down even⁶⁴, as the revolving crescent was recorded worldwide.⁶⁵

The question still remains, how would the Welsh have utilized or viewed this Saturnian phenomena? As it was Kronos and Zeus who first taught mankind of warfare, and of the weapons of the gods (sword, spear, bow and arrow, and trident), as well as of kingship,⁶⁶ it only stands to reason that mankind learned the advantage of the "high ground" in both perspective and military advancement, from the gods.

Read in the Bible on the tower,

*"5 But the Lord came down to see the city and the tower the people were building. 6 The Lord said, "If as one people speaking the same language they have begun to do this, then nothing they plan to do will be impossible for them. 7 Come, **let us go down** and confuse their language so they will not understand each other."⁶⁷ (emphasis added)*

Therefore we see that the Lord⁶⁸ came from above, and came as many (be it moons or rocks, no one knows), enjoying the superior advantage of a tower or hill above, even if that "hill" be a cloud or sky. It is the author's insistence that mankind was as a child to a father (above), and learned from Him, and worshiped and replicated Him. What things he learned, first he saw, and then tried to do and improve. Sometimes in error or profound confusion, or even comical superstitious behavior. But generally with a template and reference at hand, for at least 5,000-20,000 years. How mankind lived before Gungun Padang and Bosnia, or between them and Atlantis and from there to Gobekli Tepe and from the Tepe period to Sumer, no one knows. However,

⁶⁴ "Discourses of an Alien Sky," (series) D. Talbot <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=svfWvSHh4AY>

⁶⁵ [7]

⁶⁶ "Lost Book of Enki," Z. Sitchin

⁶⁷ Genesis 11:5-7

⁶⁸ IAO/IAU or Uchêll in Coelbren [28]

one can be certain that the learned households of kings, princes, and would-be emperors worldwide sought to invoke this authority. Not only in China⁶⁹, but also as we shall see with more evidence, in Camelot, Wales.

The Cosmic Egg or Womb

One of the most important, and most ancient, motifs, is that of the Cosmic Egg, also known as a womb. Hypothesized by Wal Thornhill to be the plasma double layer of the 'proto-Saturn'⁷⁰ it is said in the Egyptian sources⁷¹ that the one God - the Lord - was the father of his mother, his sister, whom he impregnated and gave birth to his son, which was Himself. There is no biological reconciling of this idea, and when Akhenaten tried to emulate it with full incest in his house, the priests considered he and his household an abomination and scourged them from history. Note that he took the aten to his name. He was clearly trying to tie his divine right to rule to the power that glowed around the Lord, and gave Atum-Re (or Ra) the ultimate authority over Zep Tepi. He was trying to recreate a Golden Age. Why was the age so fortuitous, if Kronos would on occasion "eat his children"?

At the time of the Earth being inside the plasma double layer inside Shamash, the reality was that there simply weren't any misalignments. All the loss of alignment, and Kronos' rage, and Zeus' rebellion and war with him, came after the fall of the Aten. This battle shook the Heavens, and dispersed all sorts of planets. Within a short span of taking over Olympus - the city on high in the sky - Zeus tossed Hades (planet Uranus) into the netherworld. While early Saturn lost its sheath, the rings formed, and Zeus 'chained' Kronos. However, it appears that in short order this brown-yellow (melin) colored goddess became, after all, the sister-wife of Zeus. Now, why would Zeus need to make her his consort? Because the alignment was weak (de-charged) but not yet broken up. And from time to time Hera (from whose system Mars or Heracles came) would be jealous of a goddess (or mortal) and strike at them. We can see that there was one planetoid or moon lost that was considered female, and she either smashed into Saturn/Hera and became Venus, or was destroyed in merging with Jupiter, or was Venus and it passed through Jupiter and emerged as Athena. It is not clear, and the oral traditions have bungled the timeline enough to make it nearly impossible to say for certain how the events unfolded with any precision. At other times Zeus would slay a god, or send Heracles (Mars) to battle a shape in the sky, and somehow another planetoid was reduced to the rubble of the "Hammered Bracelet" (asteroid belt). This too was a belt of power, that was associated with Hercules-Thor (Mars).

But at any rate, the original motif of the Fertility God(dess) was shortly the mantle of Jupiter, for we see in the Greek genesis that Zeus 'threw stones' over his shoulder to re-create mankind, and this would have been the tenuous era from 6000 years ago to 2,500 years ago at the latest, possibly earlier. The result was not that Zeus was ever considered female - he was the All-father or King of the Gods - but that he created life from nothingness. This concept was therefore borrowed from the earlier concept of the Fertility God or Heaven-Man who sat on his high throne and made life prosper in the Golden Age previous to the Younger Dryas event. The movement of Marduk - or Nibir, if it be not a planet Nine/X - appears to have been the culprit for the end of this, and a series of worldwide changes, including the introduction of our Moon, clearly a Jovian rocky moon. One of

⁶⁹ Qin Shi Huangdi named himself for the Yellow Emperor and made his funerary pyramid to be a gigantic earthen pyramid. Earth's color is yellow in China, and the center of the Celtic symbol for Earth. This symbol is throughout the Shang scripts, and is a worldwide symbol for the Four Winds or Pillars of Heaven. Earth is the cross in its center, and represents the mother (as Earth). Therefore the symbol also indicates the womb, and hill or mound of pregnancy, as we saw with the Mayans: the Lord was his own mother and birthed himself, once again as Venus. In Nordic tradition Loki was male and female, and part of Odin's household. Though for most patriarchal cultures, Mars was the preferred god as he was the God of War.

⁷⁰ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Kff_ytg0-8w

⁷¹ As the Hebrew were the Sumerians, but were for a time in Egypt, perhaps the Hebrews learned of the myth of the Aten there; or perhaps had it on their own. This would be a full 2,000 years before Troy, so there is no way of knowing how the motif transferred to anywhere in Europe.

these changes was the Great Flood. Whether this was mega-tsunamis⁷², or the rapid melt of ice sheets with simultaneous destruction of the north pole of Earth, or a Deluge caused by Saturnian rain is not yet clear. Some favor the earlier Younger Dryas dual dates of start and end, and some favor a separation of the flood event into YD and to a Sumerian age, which would separate the two events by 5,000 - 9,000 years. Can a flood myth with the details in the Bible and worldwide survive for 9,000 years?⁷³ It is difficult to tell, and hard to believe, but there are the uncanny words of Solon's priest Sonchis⁷⁴, who has described the sinking of Atlantis and how far the Greeks had sunk in knowledge,

"In the Egyptian Delta, at the head of which the river Nile divides, there is a certain district which is called the district of Sais [...] To this city came Solon, and was received there with great honour; he asked the priests who were most skilful in such matters, about antiquity, and made the discovery that neither he nor any other Hellene knew anything worth mentioning about the times of old. On one occasion, wishing to draw them on to speak of antiquity, he began to tell about the most ancient things in our part of the world-about Phoroneus, who is called "the first man," and about Niobe; and after the Deluge, of the survival of Deucalion and Pyrrha; and he traced the genealogy of their descendants, and reckoning up the dates, tried to compute how many years ago the events of which he was speaking happened. Thereupon one of the priests, who was of a very great age, said: O Solon, Solon, you Hellenes are never anything but children, and there is not an old man among you. Solon in return asked him what he meant. I mean to say, he replied, that in mind you are all young; there is no old opinion handed down among you by ancient tradition, nor any science which is hoary with age."⁷⁵

Taking this quote at face value, it is implying that the Greeks were some of those most directly wiped out, and that only Egypt was able to keep the memory of Zep Tepi and of Atlantis and an Atlantean Age, intact. Looking at the Saharan Great Flood route, it seems entirely possible, albeit hard to believe (see Figure 8).

The mystery of the First Time, or Golden Age, has been slowly unfolding for us⁷⁶, for example the discovery of disappeared islands, such as Hy-Brasil⁷⁷, Doggerland⁷⁸, Mauritius⁷⁹, Sundaland⁸⁰, etc. While this does not prove the existence of Shamash as a green midnight-star which then changes into a brown-yellow ringed and glowing planet-god(dess⁸¹), it certainly leads the credence of circumstantial evidence; as they say, "where there's smoke, there's fire."

⁷²

https://www.academia.edu/37958235/Sinking_of_Atlantis_by_Marduk_in_9577_BC_Part_4_Destruction_from_the_flood

⁷³ See [16] Part 3

⁷⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sonchis_of_Sais

⁷⁵ "Timaeus/Critias," Plato

⁷⁶ [3]

⁷⁷ <https://www.ancient-origins.net/unexplained-phenomena/hy-brasil-legendary-phantom-island-ireland-003608>

⁷⁸ <https://www.nationalgeographic.com/magazine/2012/12/doggerland/>

⁷⁹ <https://www.nationalgeographic.com.au/nature/found-a-lost-continent-deep-beneath-the-indian-ocean.aspx>

⁸⁰ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sundaland>

⁸¹ In time Venus, which emerged from Saturn at first, was seen as the new fertility goddess (at first). She was also seen as a warrior

Figure 8 - Fluvial Evidence from Tunisia through Mali, Niger, Algeria, and Mauritania

How does this figure into the Camelot myth, other than the melin color? The hill, if one observes figure 1 carefully, is shaped somewhat like an egg. Here is a closer examination of the hill:

Figure 9 - Caer Melyn close up view of obliquitous shape

While the egg shape is not overtly perfect, what is interesting is the preponderance of egg-shape references in Saturn motifs from Egypt to China to the Ohio River Valley. Starting with Egypt, as the author has shown, the Ramesses stele and similar hieroglyphics have shown that the Egyptians were able to measure the equatorial and polar diameters to within < 1% of satellite measurements.

Figure 10 - Egyptian Creation Myths, Coffin Texts depicting transfer of plasma in sky; credit: Wiki⁸²

Yet we don't always find in Egypt the exact ovoid shape, but rather the shape of an egg⁸³. In general, however, the solar orb is an ovoid/oblate shape, and not always perfectly shaped, but most definitely not a circle. See Figure 11.

Many scriptural references to the "sun" in the Egyptian Book of the Dead, Coffin Texts, and more have been translated (naturally) using the current sky as the main measure, and so this has confused scholars, Egyptologists, and anthropology in general. While it was natural to translate the sun-god as the current solar orb, there can be no doubt from the meaning of the texts, and from the depiction of the hieroglyphics that the true implication of the astronomers' recordings was proto-Saturn: 'Atum-Ra.' For atum, is the aten or amen⁸⁴ and is, ultimately the Edin itself (if it is not a region of land).

⁸² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ancient_Egyptian_creation_myths

⁸³ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Egg_\(hieroglyph\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Egg_(hieroglyph))

⁸⁴ Amen is still prayed for at the end of Christian prayers. Sumer > Hebrews in Egypt > Jews > Christians

Figure 11 - The Solar orb on the left (circle), as compared to the Flaring God on the right (egg/ovoid); aka the Bull of Heaven; credit: N. Davies

The downside to observing the myth's influence on the Kumry/Cymru people, is that with plasmaglyphs the entire world could see them, but not all would necessarily interpret them the same way. However, the fact that the Bardsian Coelbren script can be used to read the Dead Sea Scrolls, Etruscan, and other Hebrew scripts lends credibility to the Trojan origins and the "Lost Tribes" hypothesis, though it doesn't yet prove it. For one thing, it could be a remarkable coincidence, or a forced translation technique, or since the Hebrew scripts are also toroid derived plasmaglyphs, it could be a case of continued evidence of a non-diffusion co-linear evolution of communications. The author is not sure what the probability of this is, but it must be very, very low without diffusion.

The Cosmic Eye

Making this subject even more interesting, is the motif of the Cosmic Eye, which definitely supports either the Saturnian Eye (the rings on tilt, form an eye like shape) or, perhaps in continuation of or in competition with the Jovian Eye. Is the one eye of Jupiter the Great Red Spot, or the south pole? As these images are IR scans, it seems unlikely they saw the eye of the south pole, thus the Jovian Eye is likely the Great Red Spot.

Figure 12 - North (left) and South (right) poles of Jupiter in infrared; credit: NASA

So, what possibly could the Eye have to do with the *Caer Melyn* myth? Maybe nothing at all. But suppose now that we focus upon the yellow God, Saturn, and the rings. What if - and this is probably a major *if* - the ancient peoples interpreted the rings in some cultures as a weapon, rather than as the chains of Kronos, or the coffin of Osiris? In China, rings, and even the solar crest (often mistaken for the lunar crescent) were attached to spears and halberds (tridents of various design) and weaponized. In Europe the Saturnian myth became associated also with the great Scythe, as seen in Odin's weapon with which he walks and slays the giants. Now we have already said that Odin was Jupiter, so what is the deal here?

The difference is the time passage between the origins of the myths and the writing of the myths which occurred after the Martian Age of War (in the Megalithic Period, aka Age of Aries).

Please bear in mind three things:

1. The legends of the north of Europe did influence the Britains, but it isn't clear that it influenced the Druids of the Welsh, who vanished with the advent of Christianity (St. Joseph, St. Thomas, etc...) ere the Romans came.
2. The documentation of the Norse traditions did not occur until the 1500's and even later, but there isn't any reason to suspect that the gods had changed much since the Martian episode ~650-700 B.C.
3. The honoring of gods, in most traditions shared certain characteristics, but not all gods were honored with the same devotion by all cultures. For example while the war god in most cultures was Mars, for

the Mexica (Aztecs) and Pawnee-Skidee, it was Venus (the morning star), to whom the main devotion was the sacrifice of hearts.

Table 3 - Norse Cultures Father-Son Gods

Planet	Saturn's Sky	Saturn ⁸⁵	Jupiter	Mars
Age	Atlantean	Tepe	Archaic	Megalithic
Oral	Bor	Odin	Thor	Tyr ⁸⁶
Written (add 1000+ yrs)	Bran/Giant	Bor	Odin	Thor

Looking at the characters of Table 3, we notice that originally Tyr (Aries) was considered a son of the **real** All-Father, Saturn, as all gods were. But **Thor**⁸⁷ was the Mardukian hero who could slay the Bull of Heaven (ala Gilgamesh). But in later ages, when Saturn disappeared, Odin became Jupiter - the hawk one-eyed god, and Tyr became unimportant as Mars and Venus (Loki) were the main story. In such a situation, all the titans or giants would be unimportant and the main stories written would be the newer stories of the Aesir vs. Vanir, which are equivalent to the Hindu Mahabharata, Greek or Mayan Myths, rather than the Zoroastrian/Sumerian/Egyptian myths which are the older sets.⁸⁸

Could, therefore, the ring of Saturn have influenced the Caerleon and Caer Melyn ring defence system? Is it really impossible to see that the Caer Melyn ring system of a central High Lord (Uchell) surrounded by satellite (lit: moons) hillforts, each a King (or a god?) which is supposed to reflect the will of the High King in a quasi Republic oligarch, be inspired by a planet/star god that the Hebrews actually also revered as just the same sort of system in El and Elohim (the little angel-messengers of El, literally His limbs)?

⁸⁵ When Saturn flared, Odin (as Jupiter), defeated Surtur the fire-giant who threatened to bring about Ragnarok.

⁸⁶ Hence Tyr's Day (Tuesday) **and** Thor's Day (Thursday). Wodin's Day, needless to say is Wednesday.

⁸⁷ [28]; the The rune in Coelbren is related to the IAO /|\ but upside down \|\ As shown, the th or t sound is almost universally related to thunder, and the power associated with Odin-Thor

⁸⁸ The Mayans however also had access to the Olmec knowledge which may have caused more interesting myths that were unique. The author is not an expert and also the canons of the Aztecs being thus burned by Spanish priests, it is ultimately impossible to know until all the Mayan pyramid texts are translated.

Figure 13 - Saturn motif⁸⁹, Big turtle Rockshelter, Kentucky; credit: Fuller et al.⁹⁰

Figure 14 - Caer Melyn ring system; a vague hexagon is visible; credit: author⁹¹

While this evidence is, again, circumstantial, it is always a strange argument to be made that when several items all point in the same direction, that they have no meaning, relation, and are no indication at all of correlation, causation, or supportive of any hypothesis. To say none at all, would be a bridge truly too far when the Coelbren word for High King is the shape the Chinese associate with God (Man) 人, which has ↑ in it.

⁸⁹ An exact replica of the Ri 日 Shang oracle glyphs, see [26] and [28]

⁹⁰ "Rock Art of Kentucky," p. 79

⁹¹ Via Wilson & Blackett; two of the center pieces are the aforementioned spring, and a forest to visit. The final non-Camelot is Ruperra Castle (51.57031, -3.12715)

The Divine Right to Rule

What *is* the 'divine right to govern'? We know what the obnoxious French aristocracy and the Tudors thought: *they* were better than *us* and sat atop a virtual pyramid of noble blood, dignity, and lineage which legitimized their rule. Well, at least one of these is true. But why did the father's son get to inherit the kingdom, aside from the biological convenience and Darwin's Natural Selection? Around the world it seems that most cultures - but not all - adopted this system of governance, despite obvious problems inherent in its 'design'.

To answer what is the DRtR, we must first discover the reasons why it exists, and discern also what is the concept of the "will of Heaven." In the Saturn Myth, there really isn't a questioning of the right of the Lord to govern. For that matter, his son is also unquestioned King of the Gods. But in the case of Jupiter, it is a right taken *by force*, and maintained by Divine Power. The power is quasi-spiritual, definitely plasma-electrical, palpably visible in light, sound, and earthquake, and cannot be overcome. Heaven is literally that which is above the highest mountains. Olympus is King of the mountains, and Zeus is king. For the Welsh, being descendents of Troy and perhaps the Hebrews, the overlordship of Ba'al/Jehovah **was equivalent** to the lordship of Yahweh. Think now back to the Sumerians. Enlil inherits the lordship from Anu, after a short age of rule by Enki, the lesser brother. By all rights of inheritance Enki should be ruler, as he is the lord of waters and sky. But it is not so, and Enki is left to play second fiddle to the fickle, arrogant, and almost cruel Enlil-Jupiter.

By the time of the Akkadians, Marduk as Jupiter is seen as dominant, usurping the power of Heaven. How can Jupiter usurp Jupiter? Firstly, there is a transfer of cultural memory, and of story. Secondly, there is the passage of time, and finally, the change in behavior. When, in the beginning Anu overthrows Alalu, this is seen as the better brother overcoming the vain. But Enlil (a later conceptualization) is not always a happy, giving Lord who creates mankind. We see from the Greek that Zeus was wayward, and mixed with mortals and other goddesses. He was also cruel in his punishments, for example with Prometheus. How were humans perceiving Jupiter? More and more as a demon of sorts. While Odin, for example, defeated Surtur (the flare-star), when Thor comes into the story, Odin is frequently devolving into a wandering old man, killing people whimsically in order to prepare his army for the Ragnarok. There may have been plagues, floods, or uneven behavior in the earth and in crops. In short, the waywardness of the Lord was seen as a fault. There was nothing you could do about it, but it wasn't seen as *equal* to the "superior Lord" of the most "superior sun" - Shamash, which remained fixed at the pole and in the sky. Quetzalcoatl was, by all accounts, a loving and giving God, in his own time. Even in our modern time we yearn for a Golden Age, and seek to leave this planet, as if we no longer belong here, or fear our time is coming to an end. Why should it end? Because the Lord was seen, pre-Biblically, as a fertility God. But now, we have nothing chaining us to our behavior. The punishments ceased when the gods left, and Apollo and Aphrodite (sun and moon, respectively), have little at all to do with the mythic religions that formed our initial insight into the proper role of government, of kings, and the *Way* of rulership (expounded for example in the "Tao Te Ching"). The Lord that guides without commanding, capable of leading from above, and influencing everything, keeping it all in check. All the moons were as His limbs, and circled about Him (hence: Elohim). And then: it fell. He fell. As the saying goes, "God is dead."

Later, of course, the Egyptians prophesied the return of his son, the Chrissus, which would create a new Paradise Earth to last forever. Though the Jehovah's Witnesses, for example, continue this ancient religion and belief, they attribute the rule to Jove, and in that they are errant. Because Jupiter was never a permanent nor fixed Lord. He was active, lithe, and almost abusive of His power. We see multiple examples of capricious desires of the Lord in the Old Testament, as well as arbitrary punishments, often interpreted by humans to be the fault of humans. But realistically, there is little reason to suppose that humans have much to do with it, nor sin. The fear of Sin - of the moon-watcher - installed by Marduk/Enlil, and the Divine Punishment, remains strong in humanity to this very day. But in all honesty no one can say that the divine karmic

mechanism has much to do with sin, beyond natural consequences of poor decisions. Many cheats, liars, etc. live and prosper while many apparently good or innocent people suffer. In India they reckoned that Mara (the Devil) was the reverse of the triple god-head of Brahma, Shiva, Indra. The dual action of both: the Janus, was worthy of worship and fear, and the Romans were sure to place January at the darkest period of the new seasonal calendars, and to not count the month but name it for this capricious Lord. Why they did not give the name to Dionysius or some other preferable God is not clear, but what is clear is that mankind continued long after Jupiter was gone to respect the King, or at the very least fear Him.

So what is the DRtR? It is a force of personality, ultimately, imposed from on High, and by **thunder** enforced with death and power, with technological terrors of spear, sword, cavalry, chariot, and bow and arrow. It is not purely about lineage. In many places it became about that. The blood which the colt inherits from the stallion is thought to be **strong**... but not always. One must be willing to *fight* and *spill blood* and must be cunning, fast, ambitious (as Marduk was), and above all, capable to wield the Power. In human terms, until the invention of the atomic bomb, this was a metaphorical wielding, usually symbolized by a sceptre, crown, or **sword**.

In the Arthurian tradition, the sword in the stone and the Excalibur myths survive as examples of either technological advances (stones forged in stone kilns and moulds) or as elegant symbols of Christian authority. Of course, the latter is related again to the Chrissus cross, which is itself tied to the Ankh motif, and these relate directly to the Saturn myth and symbolism, demonstrated elsewhere that the “celtic cross” of the Templars and others is plainly originally a Saturnian “four winds” diagram!

Moreover, the DRtR comes with it the **authority** to interpret the Will of Heaven, which is as vague as it is meaningful. What is Heaven’s Will? In the Old Testament God - or His messengers - speak directly to Abraham, and his descendents. This should not be seen as arbitrary but a continual tradition of those who came from Mesopotamia and were witnesses to the Force, as it was applied by the Lord, his ‘angels’ (Elohim), and the fallen ones (electro air-burst comets), such as Nephilim, Annunaki, and Igigi. Their airbursts and intense destructions were *not* alien weapons but various formations of plasma shape discharges, also called thunderbirds worldwide. They were, if nothing else, devastating, and several cities were utterly destroyed. At Sodom of course the Hebrews have interpreted the meaning of its destruction to be related to some unspecified hatred the Lord had for the twin cities⁹².

But the Will of Heaven is far more than that. It is discerning the behavior of the weather, of the right heir, of the interaction of the king with God-Heaven so that he (or she in a Queen’s case) may determine what is the best case of action. Can this will of Heaven mean much more, or perhaps have a greater symbolism?

The Floating Island or Shining City

As has been recounted above, the summit of the mountain, be it a plasma step-pyramid shape in the sky or merely the summit of Heaven as moons surrounding Elohim, was seen as a floating island or a shining city with ‘gleaming towers’ or spires. It may be that these images have some influence to castle keep towers and peaks, church spires (reverence for them, and shape, etc.), and skyscrapers. However, for us, we are primarily interested in the idea of a shining city *upon a hill*, for that is the imagery that remains for us of Camelot. It is totally warranted that authors and modern scholars would seek a castle with a great keep and towers of high, magnificent views, in memory of the greatest of Dark Age cities and amongst the greatest of

⁹² Some claimed it was related to homosexuality, others to loyalties, and finally some to simple territorial disputes of rival lords to Jehovah (in the ancient alien hypothesis, as per Sitchin-Begolino <https://drive.google.com/open?id=0B8cZZ8vNfLrRTmlzQ2p1WEc1dzA>).

worldwide legend. But is it necessary that it be a castle towering, or a **towering castle** which overlooked quite a large vale, and could be seen even from the sea, as both a warning, and a hope?

Referring to Figure 9, we can see there are over 80 m, perhaps 90 m (295') of elevation change along a very steep slope, and another 80 m (262') as it descends to the M4. By the time anyone approaching would even deign to assault the hillfort mansion of His Majesty, the High King of Britain (land of those descended of Brutus), they would have been seen, and in the end, would still need to ascend nearly six hundred feet to reach just the base of the walls.

The hope of defence, of the important bay, of the center of Britain (for it was the true center at that time, and not Loegria), etc. lay in the power of Caerleon, Cardiff Castle, Arthur's Head, and of course, Caer Melyn, the Yellow Fort, which served (as it did in China) as the center of the Red, Green, Black, and White forts, as Earth does. Yellow is the center, and still is the symbol we *currently* use for Earth (see Figure 15).

Figure 15 - Chinese 5 Element System; note the cross motif in the word for Earth, and the Great man associated with Fire above, and the other plasmaglyph motifs; credit: J. Barthelemy

We are not without our connections, culturally, to this memory. While few of us are of Khumry descent, or Hebrew, Etruscan, Crimean, or Mesopotamian, the fact remains that our culture is exactly from that line:

Sumer > Babylon > Hebrews (in Egypt) > Israel > Troy > Constantinople/Crimea > Italy > Iberia > Brittany > Britain > Western civilization (America, Canada, Australia, New Zealand, and Western Europe).

Therefore, it is no surprise, that all the hallmarks of our society and civilization such as contract law, libraries, fortresses, trigonometry, coinage, writing, Republicanism, and much more come to us though just

such a movement of ideas: Sumer > Babylon > Bible > Greece > Rome > Dark Ages Europe. Thus it can be said, that Arthur's true history, and that of the Cymru, is in the history of all modern people, and that although the kingdom of Britain fell, the culture - in the sense of fairness, justice, reverence in religion, and chivalry (for we lament that we lack it nowadays) - has won the world over, in some places more than others. But it has not died, and goes on, in the West.

Conclusions?

There are no hard conclusions to draw, only more questions. There is a great deal of circumstantial evidence, conjecture, and comparative mythology. In general these are all criticisms of the technique as well, for both the Welsh people deserve their own credits and independence, and the right to tell their own story, and the historians, too, will find the lot of it discombobulating. But the hallmark of this line of investigation is to venture into *unusual* waters, and frankly, investigate life and reality on its own terms. Truly it has been said, "truth is stranger than fiction." What cozens us into believing in normalcy and regularity, will always surprise us, because after all, nothing in the history of scientific inquiry has ever turned out to be "just as it should be" for those living during the inquest. In some instances the radical departure from normalcy was so sudden, shocking, revolting, and even sinister or diabolical that mankind has rarely accepted anything new without protest and even violence. Men have been burned at the stake, or lobotomized, for their assertions.

Wilson & Blackett put their own careers and houses on the line, and paid heavy prices for their Arthurian quests, and inquiries. They have moreover triumphed, in a way, despite all of that. But it is doubtful they even suspected some of the things that have been proposed here. Rather their inquiries were of a post Egyptian nature, and not particularly interested in the motifs from the Jovian and Saturnian ages. Zep Tepi is not so important to the Welsh as their own golden age, of Arthur and the 'round table', Excalibur, Camelot, and Avalon (Affalach). But supposing that there is even a smidge of truth in this inquest, what are the implications? There are sociological ramifications, historical ones, and of course, anthropological or archaeological ones.

Consider the possibility of the need to look for stone circle fort kingdoms **worldwide** in places one least expects it: South Africa, Amazon, Sahara, Siberia, North America, and Australia. What if there are lost kingdoms all around us, and we simply have ignored them through willful, neglectful, or worst of all politically motivated *amnesia*. If this research has led the author to any conclusion it is that every culture of the modern age should trace its own current back, and back, and back until at last a Shining City emerges, be it like Dvaraka in the ocean (which is sadly neglected, and mostly unknown by the locals to the modern city), or Machu Pichu, Cahokia, Shangra La, or Atlantis. When these Shining Cities emerge, or even if they don't, test them, and the evidence, against the Saturn Myth. If it fails the inquisition, then it is simply without merit. But if it is with merit, and various aspects come into play (see Saturn Myth table and book), then reconsider [ye skeptics] the possibilities that lay on a currently bland, and seemingly abandoned hill, just north of the M4 and Cardiff. We are so very used to the mystique of Camelot we have come to doubt its very existence, and make fantastical stories about it.⁹³

But, once upon a time, it was a fortress mansion upon a steep hill, which was both the hope of a people as it was the home of their High King, and the fear of invaders. It was, truly, the central axis of a round wheel. Whether it was ever the central place of worship of Saturn will never be known. Nor is that important. All that matters is that the Lord was manifest in his power of judgment and military might in that place, where Heaven and Earth met, high upon a hill.

⁹³ Bear in mind though that despite the historical records, there may be much Bardism in this tale; for the parallel of Tewdrig to Saturn, Meurig to Jupiter, and Arthur to Mars, and their enemies to the gorgons and titans, should not be missed!

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